

Composite Strategy for Carbon Emission Control in Supply Chains: A novel model for Sustainable Management Decision Making

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Abstract

A novel composite incentive strategy for carbon emission reduction (CISCER) was developed, incorporating existing carbon emission technologies and practice of green product manufacturing and supply GMPs. The proposed strategy was tested in a cross-sectional survey using the European Customer Satisfaction Index and a partial least square design for structural equation modeling using the SmartPLS (version 3) software. Stimulating variables were tested for the effects on the willingness of supply chain managers to adopt the proposed CISCER model and findings showed that almost all except premiums had a significant influence on the perceived level of satisfaction derived by supply chain managers with the CISCER model which is directly linked to their willingness to adopt same. The correlation coefficient of most influencing variable was perceived profits (0.81), followed by perceived sustainability (0.71), perceived organizational image (0.60), perceived product value (0.56), perceived cost reduction (0.52), and premiums (0.34) being the least influential on willingness. The model was further proved and a quadratic optimization modeling approach proposed for the maximization of profits and reduction of costs. Approach and findings are relevant in the development, testing, and adoption of new strategies towards the realization of carbon emission reduction goals of firms in supply chain management.

Keywords: Supply chain management, decision support, carbon emission reduction, composite incentive strategy

Declarations of interest: none.

1. Introduction

Supply chain management has been under significant pressure in recent times owing to the vast nature of the sector as it controls the movement of goods to and from one geographical setting to the other, across continents and nations (Ahmed and Sarkar, 2018; Farajzadeh, 2018). The difficulty in decision making on the side of supply chain managers has to do with meeting international goals regarding the protection and/or creation of public goods through carbon emission reduction. Several research works done confirmed the negative effects of some manufacturing processes on the environment in light of carbon emissions (CSX Transportation, 2017; Esmaeili et al., 2009). Global climate change effects are evident enough to prove that the need to preserve the environment while making economic gains is as crucial as the survival of the human race (Abel et al., 2018; Veira et al., 2016). Finding an optimal position between satisfying both environmental and economic goals still does not exclude the need for social acceptability as a prerequisite to sustainability.

Carbon emission is obviously a global challenge and problem that many types of research done in the area of supply chain management and engineering seek to address. A survey was conducted in 2016 during the annual Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP) conference comprising of respondents from a wide range of industries, concerning their opinions of key drivers that will impact productivity in the supply chain (CSX Transportation, 2017). Both perceived future opportunities and challenges were considered, and the major key points as confirmed by the majority were ranked as follows: 1. Cost reduction; 2. Service improvement; 3. Process streamlining; 4. Expansion of transportation emission; and 5. Carbon emission reduction. Ranking has shown that supply chain managers from different backgrounds and companies are firstly interested in economic gains before environmental preservation. Carbon emission reduction was the last option considered. This makes it crucial to ensure that the reduction of carbon emission is entrenched into a regulated system that can enhance obligatory adherence in order to avoid defects in a good public provision such as free riding, prisoner's dilemma, time- dimension, government sovereignty, and diverging preferences and priorities.

Several approaches have been proposed through research such as green supply chain practices, the change from linear to closed-loop supply chain models and many others (Govindan et al., 2014; Barari et al., 2012). However, the ability for supply chain managers to make deliberate decisions that may result in losses to their organizations makes the realization of such brilliant proposals difficult (Mathiyazhagan et al., 2013; Diabat and Govindan, 2011). It is always a

difficult situation to take certain types of risks, especially when dealing with the provision of goods based on demand from consumers whose behaviors may be influenced dynamically and in uncertain manners. In as much as consumer behaviour may be studied and trends identified, there is always an amount of uncertainty. This can be substantiated by the returns of orders of goods delivered to consumers due to change of mind or unmet expectation.

Certifications for good manufacturing practices (GMPs) and other green practices have the potential to give a certain virtual positive perception about a place or an organization and its products such that this positive perception can be priced or internalized into the market system while providing a good avenue to public goods creation (Schusser and Jaraitè, 2018; Wang et al., 2018; WIPO, 2017). This is a concept which can be leveraged on in offsetting the risks associated with climate change mitigation during the struggle for reduced carbon emissions, as it is already common to the World Trade Organization (WTO). This is a form of certification that are given organizations for adhering to set standards for environmental conservation. This concept can be further extended to capture other relevant suggestive practices that have the potential to conserve the environment. It is expected that, as firms adhere to such composite strategies towards environmental sustainability, they get certified, and they are given the right to access certain benefits that offset costs incurred during environmental protection efforts, and as well make reasonable profits, as with the Eu common agricultural policy (Helming and Tabeau, 2018). This composite strategy, therefore, becomes an incentive system for supply chain organizations and serves as an insurance to offset potential risks faced as a result of efforts made towards carbon emission reduction. The main purpose of this study is to develop and propose a composite incentive system that can encourage an optimal leverage between realizing economic gains of supply chains and a reduction in carbon emission. Using the integrated lifecycle approach for products with emphasis on the food and beverage industry, this study seeks to identify strategies that hinge on environmental sustainability; link identified strategies to a form of assessment system that gives organizations the right to benefit from a string of incentives that improve organization's profit; and find out organizational willingness to adopt such composite strategy and the best means to enforced efficiently and sustainably.

2. Material and methods

The acceptance of new concepts by users has been a significant field of study for many years now. Despite the fact that many concepts and models have been suggested to explain and predict the use of a concept or technology, the TAM has been the only one which has captured the most attention and is the most widely used model. It is therefore essential for anyone willing to study customer acceptance of new concepts such as a composite incentive strategy for carbon emission reduction (CISCER) to have an appreciation of the TAM (Chuttur, 2009; Davis, 1986). It was proposed that system use is a response that can be explained or predicted by user motivation influenced by an external stimulus made up of the system's features and capabilities. In this instance, it is made clear that the TAM is based on end-user or customer motivation, system features and capabilities. In this Model, the customer (supply chain organization) becomes the middle entity which relies on an external stimulus to produce a response which is the actual acceptance and usage of the new concept (CISCER) or technology in context (Figure 1).

Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (PLS-SEM) design was used according to Sun et al. (2018) to compute the relationship between features and capabilities of the proposed CISCER and the willingness of supply chain managers to adopt and use such proposed concept. This study, therefore, was aimed at finding a way to measure how the stimulus (CISCER) and response are reflected in the motivation of supply chain managers towards adoption.

Figure 1: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1986): **a)** Simplified concept of TAM, linking a customer to external stimuli and response. **b)** A more complex, detailed model which consists of three parts- external stimuli (X1, X2, X3); user motivation (perceived usefulness, attitude towards use, perceived ease of use); and response (actual system use).

2.1 Theory/ calculation

2.1.1 Proposed CISCER Model

Figure 2: Diagram showing how external stimulus (in blue shades) and manifest variables (attached) influence composite features of operability of the CISCER (middle area), willingness of supply chain managers and actual adoption of proposed model. The adoption is subject to M&E and potential future reforms.

2.2 CISCER Model Description and optimization

This model basically is made up of an inner and outer model with the outer model sub-divided into stimuli and response. The stimuli of the outer model consist of variables such as product value, premiums, organizational image, cost reduction, profits, and sustainability. These are variables that usually inform the decision making process of supply chain managers among others, and are key in determining the willingness of managers to accept and use the CISCER model. The second part of the outer model is the actual adoption and usage of the model after decisions are reached based on the satisfaction gotten by management from the stimulating variables, hence the response variable.

Let us take outer model stimulating variables to be ρ and response variable, μ . Thus, if the decision to use the model is μ , then μ depends on the levels and cumulative effects of ρ . That is:

$$\mu = \sum \rho \times Kc \dots\dots\dots eqn 1.$$

where K is a constant calculated based on the levels of carbon emission reduction, c .

The value of K depends on the technology used for carbon emission reduction calculation by the supply chain organization. It is worth noting that the values obtained for ρ largely depend on the extent of internalization of green production and GMPs adopted by supply chains, which in turn influence values recorded for K . The advantage of this model is that, in as much as it encourages the use of standardized criteria for the calculation of K , it allows organizations to manipulate their strategies to suit their specific needs and for specific carbon emission reduction goals.

By introducing the cost for the implementation of appropriate green practices and GMPs, *eqn 1* can be rewritten as:

$$\mu = \sum \rho \times Kc - C \dots\dots\dots eqn 2.$$

where C stands for the cost of implementation and is expected to be negative in order to yield expected response, μ .

This model can be optimized using ρKc and C as independent variables, with μ as a dependent variable which should be maximized while maintaining cost, C at its barest minimum.

Using $\mu = f(\rho Kc) + C$

$$\mu = b_0 + b_i \rho Kc_1 + b_2 \rho Kc_2 + b_{12} \rho Kc_1 \rho Kc_2 + b_{11} \rho Kc_1^2 + b_{22} \rho Kc_2^2 + C \dots\dots eqn 3.$$

As the willingness (μ) of supply chain organizations is dependent on the level of improved profit margins, it is expected that optimizing for a higher μ will directly reflect profits maximization and sustainability of the firm, hence the appropriateness of the model.

Table 1: Survey questions pertaining to PLS-SEM

Latent Variables	Manifest Variables
Perceived Image	Q1. How you perceive the adoption of the CISCER to boost the image of your organization? Q2. To what extent do you think consumers will be drawn to your products and services due to CISCER adoption? Q3. To what extent will the proposed CISCER label you as environmentally friendly?
Perceived Profit	Q4. Do you think the adoption of the CISCER will enhance your revenue? Q5. How do you rate the effect of the CISCER on repurchase intentions of your consumers? Q6. How do you rate the effectiveness of the CISCER on products/services pricing and income?
Perceived Value	Q7. Please rate the quality of products/services considering the effects of CISCER adoption. Q8. Does the CISCER support high quality per the performance standards of your organization? Q9. Do you feel customers will value the level of quality you provide based on your adoption of the CISCER?
Perceived Premiums	Q10. To what extent will premiums earn boost your profit margins? Q11. Is this profit margin from premiums enough to encourage your decision to adopt the CISCER? Q12. Please rate the effect of premiums on consumer purchasing decision based on the level of quality of products/services?
Perceived Sustainability	Q13. How will the CISCER sustain the profitability of your organization? Q14. Concerning the features of the CISCER, how do you rate its long term applicability? Q15. Do you think the adoption of the CISCER is socio-economically and ecologically sound?
Perceived Cost Reduction	Q16. Considering the features of the CISCER, rate the effects on production cost reduction. Q17. Rate how the CISCER will help reduce transportation cost. Q18. Rate how the CISCER will help reduce raw material acquisition cost. Q19. Rate how the CISCER will help reduce cost related to wages.
Satisfaction	Q20. Overall, how satisfied are you with the proposed CISCER? Q21. Does the CISCER meet the goals of your business?

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Reliability of model

The reliability of both the outer and inner models were tested by the goodness of fit (GoF) test, with and without bootstrapping, factor loading coefficients, Cronbach’s alpha, and F-square value. Factor loading coefficients for all

manifest variables ranged between 0.57 to 0.96 with a minimum Cronbach's alpha value of 0.72 and a maximum of 0.84. An f-square value greater than zero was realized (0.425), and these showed the reliability of both inner and outer models.

3.2 Effects of stimulating variables on a willingness to adopt proposed CISCER model

Figure 3 shows the results per the acceptable criteria of the algorithm calculation. These were to ensure that the results were reliable. According to the algorithm quality criteria for PLS-SEM, an R² value of 0.75 showed that the latent variable, perceived satisfaction was explained to a high degree (75%) by the manifest variables.

Figure 3: Mapping the relationship between stimulating variables and willingness to use CISCER model

From path coefficients for stimulating latent variables measured, almost all except premiums had a significant influence on the perceived level of satisfaction derived by supply chain managers with the CISCER model which is directly linked to their willingness to adopt same. The most influencing variable was perceived profits (0.81), followed by perceived sustainability (0.71), perceived organizational image (0.60), perceived product value (0.56), perceived cost reduction (0.52), and premiums (0.34) being the least influential (Figure 3).

The measurement of acceptance and use of the CISCER model, like any other model, is based on cross-sectional empirical data on the intentions of its adoption by potential users such as managers. In this case, the measurement only considers perceived scores based on model features presented in questionnaires. When models need practical use, pilot runs are carried out to ascertain actual performance over a short period (Shen, 2006). This study assessed the willingness of supply chain managers to adopt and use the CISCER model based on their overall satisfaction with the model. Findings revealed that perceived profit to be made by the adoption of the model was the main factor influencing potential adoption and usage by 81 percent (Figure 3). This result is similar to others in works done in the area of management decision modeling as profit maximization is a key and the main factor to consider in measuring the achievement of organizational performance (Lessmann et al., 2018; Ahumada and Villalobos, 2009; Shen, 2006).

The need expressed by supply chain organizations in the reduction of costs of production through streamlining efforts, the expansion of transportation, the utilization and valorization of by-products in closed loops, and sustained profits, all point towards the general concepts of cost and profit (Kim et al., 2018).

4.0 Conclusion

The study proposed and tested the CISCER model to ascertain the level of willingness of supply chain managers in its adoption and use for the reduction of carbon emissions through GMPs and internalization of other green production practices. Stimulating variables of the outer model substantially (0.75) explained the response factor (willingness). All stimulating variables except for premiums had a significant influence on the response, with perceived profit having the highest score (0.81). A quadratic optimization model was also proposed to understand how best stimulating variables could be adjusted to attain the highest level of satisfaction.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors herein wish to make known that there are no conflicts of interest whatsoever connected to this study and publication of its findings.

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